

Benchmarking practices for the recycling of PVB interlayer film in laminated glass applications

V. Nikitakos¹, A.D. Porfyris¹, K. Beltsios¹, C.D. Papapspyrides¹

¹ Laboratory of Polymer Technology, School of Chemical Engineering, Zographou Campus, National Technical University of Athens, 15780 Athens, Greece;

Laminated glass is obtained by bonding two glass layers using a polymeric interlayer (PVB) and it is mainly applied in car windshields, construction and photovoltaics. Its use is constantly growing with a total current amount of PVB sheet for the automotive and construction industries equal to ca. 120 million kg per year; as a result the end-of-life of the laminated glass should be addressed [1]. In addition, PVB has a high value with an average price of 5,24 €/kg and it is usually mixed with ca. 30% w/w plasticizer, which is also valuable, and currently it is being landfilled after the end of life.

In this work it was attempted to create a recycling strategy by determining the critical parameters for sorting PVB such as molecular weight, plasticizer type, plasticizer content and yellowness index. The characterization methods include FTIR, MFR, DSV, TGA, DSC and plasticizer extraction processes aiming at establishing a technology for this recycling process (see Table 1) [2]. Overall, this benchmarking strategy aims at the development of a multi-sensor sorting tool for the determination of PVB waste streams that are potentially appropriate for loop-recycling of this interlayer film.

Table 1: Key properties for benchmarking PVB wastes

Sample name	MFR (g/10min)	[η] (dL/g)	Plasticizer (% w/w)	Yellowness Index
PVB reference	2.45 \pm 0.13	2.45 \pm 0.13	33 \pm 1	1.12%
PVB waste	2.25 \pm 0.10	1.92 \pm 0.10	28 \pm 1	-5.01%

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References

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